

NOTES

Co-ordination Chemistry of Quadrivalent Uranium—Some New Hexahalouranates (IV) of Organic Bases

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Uranium tetrachloride is known to form hexachlorouranate (IV) ion and, in fact, its salts with univalent metal ions are long known. Recently¹, quite a number of organic derivatives of Uranium tetrachloride and also hexachlorouranates have appeared in the literature.

The present study has been undertaken to investigate the properties of hexahalo (chloro-, bromo-, and also thiocyanato-) uranates (IV) and (V) of organic bases. Starting from uranyl acetate and using chemical method of reduction in presence of strong hydrochloric acid medium the following compounds have been isolated for the first time in crystalline form and have been characterised by chemical analysis and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Compound	U(%)		Cl(%)		N(%)		μ_{eff} , B.M.
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
Bis-pyridinium hexachlorouranate (IV), tetrahydrate, $(\text{PyH})_2[\text{UCl}_6] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Green	34.60	34.86	30.80	31.23	4.29	4.10	2.99
2,2'-bipyridinium hexachlorouranate (IV) $\text{BipyH}_2[\text{UCl}_6]$. Pale greenish yellow	39.00	39.10	34.70	35.01	4.28	4.60	2.05
1,10-Phenanthroline hexachlorouranate (IV) $\text{PhenH}_2[\text{UCl}_6]$. Pale greenish yellow	37.71	37.61	33.25	33.69	4.28	4.42	2.44

The marked deviation of the result of magnetic susceptibility measurement in 2,2'-bipyridyl salt for a d^2 configuration of quadrivalent species like uranium (IV) does not clearly indicate that the 'spin only' formula is inapplicable here. However, this is under further investigations and the result will be reported later on.

The other salts of this series with 8-oxyquinoline (oxine), aniline, ethylene diamine, propylene diamine etc., and the corresponding bromo- and thiocyanato- compounds also have been isolated and are under detailed investigations which will be published later on.

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